

ELEKTRON TIJORAT JARAYONLARINI YARATISHDA JINJA SHABLONLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada elektron tijorat jarayonlarini onlayn savdo saytlari ko‘rinishida yaratish uchun veb texnologiyalar asosida dasturlash va unda mashhur freymvorklarning qo‘llanilishi haqida so‘z boradi. HTML kodlari orasida interaktiv ifodalarning, xususan Python dasturlash tili ifodalarning qo‘llanilishi bevosita Jinja shablonlari asosida yaratilishi ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan. Shuningdek, Python dasturlash tili asosida ishlovchi Django freymvorki haqida ma’lumotlar berilgan. Jinja kodlarining Django freymvorki tizimida qo‘llanilishi haqida ham ma’lumot keltirilgan.

Tayanch so‘z va iboralar: *elektron tijorat, raqamli iqtisodiyot, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, onlayn, jinja, shablon, django, freymvork, funksiya, HTML.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ШАБЛОНОВ JINJA ДЛЯ СОЗДАНИЯ ПРОЦЕССОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ

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Аннотация. В статье рассказывается о программировании на основе веб-технологий и использовании популярных фреймворков для создания процессов электронной коммерции в виде сайтов интернет-магазинов. Среди HTML-кодов показано, что использование интерактивных выражений, в частности выражений языка программирования Python, создается непосредственно на основе шаблонов Jinja. Также представлена информация о фреймворке Django на основе языка программирования Python. Он также предоставляет информацию о том, как код Jinja используется в среде Django.

Ключевые слова и фразы: *электронная коммерция, цифровая экономика, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, онлайн, jinja, шаблон, django, фреймворк, функция, HTML.*

USING JINJA TEMPLATES TO CREATE E-COMMERCE PROCESSES

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Annotation. The article talks about programming based on web technologies and the use of popular frameworks to create e-commerce processes in the form of online shopping sites. Among the HTML codes, the use of interactive expressions, in particular Python programming language expressions, is shown to be created directly based on Jinja templates. Information about the Django framework based on the Python programming language is also provided. It also provides information on how Jinja code is used in the Django framework.

Keywords and phrases: *e-commerce, digital economy, information and communication technologies, online, jinja, template, django, framework, function, HTML.*

If you look at today's mass media, you can see many articles about the achievements in the field of information and communication technologies in our country. The increasing level of information transmission of local and international Internet channels in our country also creates the ground for the introduction of an electronic commerce system based on information and communication technologies. In particular, electronic document circulation systems are being introduced, electronic payments are being developed, and the legal framework created in the field of electronic commerce is being improved. In order to implement the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Commerce" in our republic, large-scale measures for the further development of electronic commerce using modern information and communication technologies have been implemented. The adoption of e-commerce laws dates back to 2004. The Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Commerce" [1] was signed on 29.04.2004 with No. 614-II. The law was later amended in 2004. "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Commerce" [2] The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. [3]

E-commerce web pages can be created in different ways. It can be created using ready-made platforms. With the WooCommerce plugin on the WordPress platform, with the VirtueMarket platform on the Joomla platform, the OpenCart platform, the OcStore platform, 1cBitrix and many other ready-made solutions can be cited as examples. The advantages of these platforms are that users with no experience in web programming can easily create their own online magazine.[4]

When the online magazine being created is required to be professional, it is necessary to turn to web programming. As one of them, the Django framework working in the Python programming language can be cited as an example.

Django is a free web framework for web applications written in the Python programming language. The design is created based on the MVC template. This project is supported by the Django Software Foundation. Its first version was presented on July 21, 2005.

A site created in the Django framework is created in the form of several applications, which can be disconnected and used. This situation makes it different from other frameworks.[5]

Russell Keith-Magee, Adrian Holovaty, Simon Willison, Jacob Kaplan-Moss, Wilson Miner are mentioned as the creators of this framework.

Here's an example to output Hello World in this framework:

```
1 from django.http import HttpResponse
2
3 def hello(request):
4     return HttpResponse("Hello world")
```

Figure 1. Publish Hello World in the Django framework.

The Django framework is widely used and can be used to build sites in many ways. According to itproger.com, the following websites are built using the Python programming language and the Django framework. YouTube (the world's

largest video hosting company owned by Google. It is not necessary to praise the popularity of this site too much), Google Search (Google has been using the Python programming language in its products for a long time. They have a good understanding of the capabilities of this language and try to use it as much as possible They use the Python programming language and the Django framework in their products.), DropBox (It is the world's largest cloud platform. You can store any information there, and synchronize it with computers and other mobile devices.), Instagram (It is the world's largest social network. Users use their can share their photos, videos and other information, participate in likes and other ratings.), Reddit (Reddit is a large social news project site. Users can post articles on various topics, leave comments for them, vote for them t), Pinterest (Pinterest resource is similar to Instagram social network. Here users share their various photos. Only here the user can easily find the pictures he is interested in), Quora (the Quora site is similar to the "Otety Mail.ru" site, where users can find answers to many questions they are interested in.), Yahoo Maps (Yahoo mainly used Node.js in its platform But Python language was also used to work with maps. In the CIS countries, this online map is not very popular, Spotify (find and listen to music for free), Onion (a satirical newspaper website), etc.

What do you need to know when creating a website based on this framework? Given that this framework runs in Python, knowledge of the Python programming language is a must. At the same time, given that this framework is intended for creating websites, it will be useful to have knowledge of HTML and CSS at the minimum level, and in addition - knowledge of JavaScript and PHP.

Web pages use special code to display the interactive information of the Django framework between HTML codes. Using special code known as jinja, it is possible to create interactive content directly with the data, checking conditions, looping arrays, printing variables, and more.

Jinja is a templating tool for the Python programming language. It's like a Django templater that serves as an environment for executing Python expressions. This is a text template. Therefore, it allows you to create markings of any

appearance. Licensed under the BSD license.[6] Expressions in Jinja are given in double brackets. For example:

```
>>> from jinja2 import Template
>>>
>>> Template("{{ 10 + 3 }}").render()
'13'
>>> Template("{{ 10 - 3 }}").render()
'7'
>>>
>>> Template("{{ 10 // 3 }}").render()
'3'
>>> Template("{{ 10 / 3 }}").render()
'3.3333333333333335'
>>>
>>> Template("{{ 10 % 3 }}").render()
'1'
>>> Template("{{ 10 ** 3 }}").render()
'1000'
>>>
```

Variables can be printed in this environment. The following example shows simple variable printing:

```
>>> Template("{{ var }}").render(var=12)
'12'
>>> Template("{{ var }}").render(var="hello")
'hello'
>>>
```

It is also possible to print lists, dictionaries, tuples and user classes[7]:

```

>>> Template("{{ var[1] }}").render(var=[1,2,3])
'2'
>>> Template("{{ var['profession'] }}").render(var={'name':'tom', 'age':
25, 'profession': 'Manager' })
'Manager'
>>> Template("{{ var[2] }}").render(var=("c", "c++", "python"))
'python'
>>> class Foo:
...     def __str__(self):
...         return "This is an instance of Foo class"
...
>>> Template("{{ var }}").render(var=Foo())
'This is an instance of Foo class'
>>>

```

You can create a function in Jinja and use it. To use the function, you need to call it:

```

>>> def foo():
...     return "foo() called"
...
>>>
>>> Template("{{ foo() }}").render(foo=foo)
'foo() called'
>>>

```

Previously, `HttpResponse` was used to print data. This approach is wrong. This is because the information contained in many HTML tags is transmitted over a single line. It is recommended to use the `render` function instead. This function is capable of compressing many large HTML templates through the Jinja templating tool. When calling HTML templates, the mandatory parameter `request` and the location of the template file are shown as parameters.[8]

Create a template. All templates will be located in the templates folder. Django automatically merges all folders into a single templates folder. Because of this feature, files with the same name can cause problems. And to get out of the problematic situation, it is recommended to place all templates in an additional folder with the name of the application. For example, in the form "home/templates/home/shablon.html". A basic structure for all HTML files can be created:

```
<body>
    {% block content %}
    {% endblock %}
</body>
```

Figure 2. Basic structure for HTML files

It is possible to change the block content by creating HTML blocks within the base template. To do this, create a new HTML file and inherit from the base file structure:

```
{% extends "PATH TO HTML FILE" %}

{% block content %}
    <div>ADD ANY CODE HERE</div>
{% endblock %}
```

Figure 3. Changing the basic HTML file structure

It can be added to other templates by creating a small code. It is recommended to place such pieces of software code in a separate folder called includes. Inside the folder, a simple HTML file is created and the Jinja markup is done there:

```
{% block content %}  
    <div>ADD ANY CODE HERE</div>  
{% endblock %}
```

Figure 4. Jinja markup code in an HTML file

To include such files, the "include" directive is used:

```
{% include "PATH TO FILE" %}
```

Figure 5. Attaching an HTML file

The list of templaters as mentioned above is quite extensive. In the list related to the Python programming language, names such as Django, Genshi, Jinja, Jinja2, Kid, Mako, web2py can be cited as examples.

Genshi is a template engine for XML-based dictionaries written in Python. Genshi is used to easily import the generated product into XML-based languages, usually HTML, and to reuse elements between documents. Genshi's syntax is based on Kid, but its architecture is different. Instead of compiling templates into Python code, Genshi aims to implement some of its functionality at a faster template processing time by dynamically processing templates using a stream-based API.[9]

Mako is a template library written in Python. Mako is an embedded Python (ie Python Server Page) language that defines the familiar ideas of componentization and inheritance. The Mako template is used by Reddit.[10]

Web2py is an open source web application framework written in the Python programming language. Web2py allows web developers to program dynamic web content using Python. Web2py is designed to help reduce tedious web

development tasks such as building web forms from scratch, although a web developer can create a form from scratch if needed.[11]

Their complete list and comparative analytical information can be found on the Wikipedia site.[12]

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